

AUTOMATED JOINING AND ASSEMBLY OF THERMOPLASTIC FUSELAGE STRUCTURES FOR THE AIRCRAFT FACTORY OF TOMORROW

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ABSTRACT:

This paper gives an overview of the objectives of the MultiFAL project – a sub-project of Large Passenger Aircraft (LPA) within the framework of the European research program Clean Sky 2 funded by the EU's Horizon 2020 program. The MultiFAL project partners will demonstrate the technological and economic feasibility of highly automated joining and assembly processes for thermoplastic aircraft structures. Therefore, a full-scale demonstrator for the assembly and joining of two thermoplastic aircraft half shells will be built up at the Fraunhofer IFAM facilities in Stade.

1. INTRODUCTION

Lightweight design is a key approach to reduce CO₂ emissions of aircrafts, which is one of the primary goals of the vision "Flightpath 2050" of the European Commission [4]. One of the most promising lightweight materials regarding this objective are carbon fibre reinforced plastics (CFRP) as they offer a remarkably high strength-to-weight-ratio.

However, based on currently primarily used thermoset CFRP materials the lightweight potential of aircraft fuselage structures is not exhausted. Reason for this is that the joining method for thermoset CFRP structures, namely riveting, requires pre-drilled holes in the fuselage shells resulting in thicker fuselage material to ensure adequate safety.

A new approach to overcome this challenge would be the application of thermoplastic CFRP materials for fuselage structures in combination with thermoplastic welding as the preferred joining method. The big advantage of thermoplastic welding in contrast to riveting is that there is no need for pre-drilled holes in the structures resulting in

thinner fuselage shells still ensuring adequate safety. However, thermoplastic CFRP materials are typically more expensive than thermoset CFRP materials. Due to this, the additional material costs have to be compensated by significantly lower manufacturing costs. To achieve this a high degree of automation in combination with a significant reduction of lead-time is essential. Concerning the joining process thermoplastic welding of the longitudinal joint and frame couplings will be in focus. In order to gain as much knowledge as possible two different weld seam designs for the longitudinal joint, namely overlapping joint and butt joint, will be demonstrated by the project partners Fraunhofer IFAM, FFT Produktionssysteme GmbH, CT engineering group and AIMEN Centro tecnologico. Furthermore, different welding methods will be used to gain comprehensive knowledge about thermoplastic welding processes.

Figure 1: Project vision of future aircraft assembly

The focus of this paper lies on the concept and design of the full scale joining and assembly demonstrator especially focusing on the elaborated robot-based flexible fuselage handling technology (flexible holding fixture) which allows a position and shape adjustment of the fuselage shells, see figure 1. Furthermore, a comparison of different welding technologies will be presented. As the project has just started and is in the concept phase, no final concepts or processes are presented in this paper. Rather, it should be understood as a status survey.

2. DEVELOPMENT AND DEMONSTRATION

To achieve weight and cost savings for the upcoming aircraft programs, completely new system and system installation architectures optimized for a modular and flexible manufacturing process are required. For a sustainable impact on industrial production and assembly, the decoupling of cabin adaptation, system installation and structural scope must be accomplished. This requires the use of advanced joining options on both fuselage and part level.

By combining technological elements from many different scenarios, the demonstrator and demonstration value can be significantly increased in order to validate the best possible technological and architectural concepts. The demonstrator will not be limited to a single scenario since elements of different fuselage designs will be considered.

The demonstrator represents a typical single aisle fuselage segment with a length of 8 m and a diameter of 4 m. This enables the validation of a number of important technological concepts in a close-to-industry environment.

To demonstrate the economic advantage of highly integrated thermoplastic CFRP structures a pre-equipped upper and lower shell including a pre-equipped passenger floor module (figure 2) will be joined by means of thermoplastic welding. For this, the PARAMONT assembly research facility [5] at Fraunhofer IFAM in Stade (figure 3) will be used.

Figure 2: Visualization of the fuselage mock-up

The PARAMONT facility is a unique robotic set-up to develop highly efficient solutions for aircraft assembly processes with an enhanced level of maturity. It allows a highly automated assembly of aircraft structural parts, e.g. clips, stringers or frame structures. Even the handling of full-scale fuselage shells is possible. The main elements of the facility are three industrial robots on a linear rail equipped with end-effectors for assembly processes on the

one hand and several parallel robot cinematics (hexapods) and linear actuators each equipped with vacuum grippers for the handling of large aircraft structures, e.g. fuselage shells, on the other.

Figure 3: PARAMONT assembly facility in Stade

The following processes will be provided by the PARAMONT assembly facility in order to execute the tasks of MultiFal:

1. Automated geometry measurement and tolerance management;
2. Handling and manipulation of the fuselage shell segments with flexible vacuum-gripper-end-effectors to adjust shape and position based on measurement data;
3. Fine adjustment of the joining gap according to the welding requirements based on measurement data;
4. Welding of the parts ensuring correct welding parameters, e.g. pressure and temperature;
5. Online-Monitoring of the assembly and welding process to ensure quality.

In the following, the individual systems of the PARAMONT facility are described. One main component of the PARAMONT facility is a flexible actuator-field consisting of up to ten hexapods, which are operated by a master-slave control principle.

Figure 4: Flexible holding fixture

The hexapods, which are installed vertically, are parallel robot kinematics with six degrees of freedom. With their vacuum-gripper-end-effectors they are able to handle and manipulate large fuselage shell structures, see figure 4. The vacuum-gripper-end-effectors consist of three vacuum-grippers each with a limit stop fixed on a triangular base plate, see figure 5. The vacuum-grippers are also used in combination with linear actuators that are installed in the roof module of the PARAMONT facility, see figures 4 and 5.

Figure 5: Vacuum-gripper-end-effector

In the vacuum-gripper the vacuum is applied to pull the shell against the limit stop to endure a defined position. When the shell parts are attached, the hexapods are able to manipulate the parts within maximum force regulations, which is a force of up to 1000 N. To ensure this, force sensors are integrated in the vacuum-gripper-end-effectors. The design allows a safe handling of the elements with a minimum of deformation within the kinematics.

The measuring devices used for referencing and shape-measurement are laser-optical coordinate measurement systems with high precision. Whilst laser trackers are used to incrementally measure defined single 3D-positions of typically pre-applied retroreflective targets, laser scanners or laser radars are used to directly measure or rather scan the surfaces of the parts.

In the use case of MultiFAL a laser tracker will be needed for the global referencing and positioning of the shells with respect to the inertial coordinate system of the PARAMONT facility and the robots. For further fine adjustments of the gap between the shells a laser scanner in combination with a laser tracker will be used, see figure 6. Furthermore, 1D- and 2D-laser-sensors will continuously monitor and correct the robot path during the joining process to meet the required tolerances.

Figure 6: Laser tracker combined with laser scanner

As mentioned before the MultiFal demonstrator depicts many scenarios in order to be able to compare different technologies. With regard to the welding process, ultrasonic welding, resistance welding and conduction welding are in focus.

Ultrasonic welding is a process which uses high frequency (ultrasonic) movements of a sonotrode-end-effector to induce ultrasonic vibration into the welding zone, creating dynamic shear stress, which is then transformed to heat [1]. This local deformation and heat generation between surfaces results in join formation in the interface area. Ultrasonic welding can be applied to amorphous and semi-crystalline polymers. In both cases the process works better if the welding surfaces are equipped with energy directors [2]. Since ultrasonic welding is a well-established, fast and very energy efficient technology, highly productive processes are possible [3].

A limitation of ultrasonic welding is that it requires physical contact between the welded parts and the welding end-effector, which can limit the geometries that can be welded. Additionally, it is typically limited to low modulus thermoplastics and due to high thermal gradients stresses can be induced into the substrates. Furthermore, ultrasonic welding is

typically used for point-by-point-welding whilst continuous welding with a moving end-effector is still under development.

In contrast to this, the basis for resistance welding is an inserted electrically conductive insert or implant between the parts to be joined. The heat is generated by electricity passing through the insert (resistance heating) during the welding process. The process is fast, simple to control, generates a homogeneous temperature distribution in the seam and can be easily applied for large structures. Moreover, the thickness of the composite (laminate) is irrelevant, and the weld can be re-heated having potential for repair requirements [3].

For conduction welding a hot iron is used to conduct heat through one of the parts to be joined into the joining area. Though this thermal process is well reproducible and leads to good seam quality, productivity rates and the bonding process are limited due to heat dissipation [1].

The welding processes mentioned will be used for longitudinal joints and frame coupling installation. To analyze the different technologies and scenarios, an inline monitoring system based on thermography and electromechanical impedance (EMI) measurement, developed with the partners Fraunhofer LBF and Fraunhofer ENAS, will be used. It will allow a continuous condition monitoring of the structures during the process. By this a systematic validation of the welding process will be possible.

3. CONCLUSION

Within the MultiFAL project the technological and economic feasibility of welding processes for thermoplastic aircraft shells will be demonstrated. For this, a full scale test setup for automated assembly and joining processes of a multifunctional fuselage demonstrator will be developed focusing on the longitudinal joints and frame couplings, see figure 7. In order to gain as much knowledge as possible from the research project, different welding methods will be used. Besides the welding technology itself, also metrology based highly automated handling and assembly processes will be in focus.

Figure 7: Final assembly process

The work performed will be an important step towards implementation of thermoplastic carbon fiber materials for future aircrafts.

4. ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

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